

IN HIGHER EDUCATION, INFRARED AND ULTRAVIOLET RAYS ARE STUDIED

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Abstract. *The article examines one of the main socio-economic reforms taking place in our country – changes made to the education system. The fact that a person can express views on the world, and the environment and perceive it, does not prove that the family, or rather, the worldview and the emergence of thoughts and ideas are formed in the process of education. In the process of introducing a system of continuing education for the younger generation of teachers with pedagogical skills, only qualified personnel can participate in training and upbringing. The best teachers of other teachers in this process can provide training in pedagogical skills and experience, and their activities should be enriched with best practices in creative use of it. The teacher's pedagogical skills are largely manifested in the preparation of the audience. Because of the essence of their training sessions, according to which the main job is to train teachers. For this reason, the scientific, ideological, and social drive to live up to the age of the entire world requires that it be appropriate to the level of training and interest. One of the great men, Abu Nasr Farabi, wrote in his treatise *On the Mind* that such people are said to be intelligent – they will have a virtuous, highly discussed, good, useful job, and an excellent talent for discovering and inventing what is necessary." Young people have knowledge, which is why using different methods is important for developing independent thinking abilities. In the course of classes, various effective methods are used that motivate young people to work with independent thinking and help to increase the number of lessons. Therefore, in higher education, the topic of infrared and ultraviolet rays is important for improving the methodology of conducting classes using various methods. During the lesson, it is emphasized that the use of infrared and ultraviolet rays in medicine, agriculture, technology, the military sphere, astronomy, photography, and the atmosphere is important for improving the effectiveness of the lesson if the teacher explains it on a schedule.*

Keywords: *seeds, medicine, agriculture, technology, military sphere, astronomy, photography, atmosphere.*

INTRODUCTION. Then check if the sunlight spectrum has also detected the presence of light that the human eye doesn't notice. Red light in the sunlight spectrum

($\lambda_q = 0.76 \mu\text{m}$) from this point on is called invisible infrared light for most light sources.

Located at the edge of the spectrum of invisible light rays, ultraviolet light is called violet cast mining. Emits infrared rays in nature, all solid bodies, atoms, and molecules of any substance that can be detected by their appearance due to the randomness associated with this.

It is known that light directed at any substance is a heater of this substance. In addition, the degree of warming, such as an increase in the temperature of a substance or a decrease in the temperature of a substance, also depends on the length of light waves.

OBJECT AND METHODOLOGY OF THE EXPERIMENT. When organizing a lesson using modern pedagogical technologies, the teacher, first of all, requires a creative approach. Because the creative teacher is always up to date with the news, and curious, he needs

to work tirelessly on himself and keep up with the times. A teacher in this spirit can prepare an independent thinker, a modern person who can explain his opinion to others, and a highly spiritual specialist. At the same time, improving the effectiveness of the lesson will also require classes, textbooks, methodological manuals, and scientific literature enriched with modern pedagogical technologies.

New developments in the subject to prepare the lesson, you just need to ask questions and answers to a group of transfer students whose knowledge level is not limited and consider several other questions, but all of them in a new group on the subject from the teacher who, in your opinion, is the reason, can explain the topic of several tasks based on infrared and ultraviolet rays. These tasks consist of the following:

To measure the temperature, you must have a sensitive thermometer. As such a thermometer, a movable plate is used to determine surface contamination – a bolometer.

The principle of operation of polymerization is as follows:

Hitting the light plate with a light heats the plate. This will change its electrical resistance. Measuring changes in resistance allows you to detect temperature changes. As we know, in an experiment to test the energy distribution in the spectrum of an electric arc, a black plate, a sensitive element of the instrument, is observed when the temperature rises as it approaches the red edge of the spectrum. The sensor element heats up more if the plate is moved beyond the red limit of the spectrum. Electromagnetic waves that cause such heating of the sensor element are called infrared waves. Infrared rays are less refracted than red rays, and their wavelengths range from 0.76 microns to 350 microns.

It is very important to know how the aerodynamic heating of surfaces in the military area by infrared rays affects all equipment for fast-flying aircraft and missiles. One-way overheating is dangerous for the structure, in which it can bend, the surfaces of the aircraft's wings can tilt, and the engines can fail. When studying these phenomena, incandescent lamps with infrared radiation are placed near the heated surface and heated in the same way as the aerodynamic incandescence itself. Surfaces are heated to 1300-1400 degrees.

Infrared methods are widely used to study the decay reaction of aviation and rocket fuel during combustion, as well as to study the combustion products. Infrared spectroscopic analysis is also used in the petroleum industry because of its high accuracy and speed compared to conventional chemical analysis. In the chemical industry, infrared technologies are used to monitor continuous chemical processes.

Even outside the violet region of the spectrum, the device feels a temperature rise. Such waves are called ultraviolet waves. These rays are more refracted than violet rays, which have a shorter wavelength than violet light (for example, B-E-G-0.4 microns), with a wavelength that ranges from 0.4 microns to 0.005 microns. Ultraviolet light does not cause the sensation of vision, since the frequency of vibrations of this light is large, and the wavelength is very small. But this light has a powerful effect on the retina and skin of the eyes, absorbing them. Ultraviolet rays from the sun are not fully absorbed in the upper atmosphere. This is why it is impossible to go without glasses for a long time when walking in the snow on high mountains. Because glass absorbs a certain amount of ultraviolet light, even white-glass glasses protect your eyes from UV rays. I must say that small doses of ultraviolet radiation have a healing effect on a person, especially useful for young people, and these rays closely contribute to the growth and hardening of the body.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. We should also briefly mention the importance of teaching the topic of infrared and ultraviolet rays in agriculture. Infrared methods are used to determine the nutrient capacity of the soil layers to be analyzed, and to identify minerals that are not enough in their composition. It is necessary to determine in time what substances are missing from the soil and plants. The agrotechnical technique allows you to take measures and measurements. In addition, it is possible to analyze fertilizers, organic phosphates poisons, and chemicals using recording infrared spectrometers. After irradiating seeds with infrared rays before planting, their germination rate increases, they germinate quickly and evenly, and their development and yield are high. When the seed is exposed to infrared light, it absorbs these rays, and its temperature rises sharply. This means that seeds that are not suitable for sowing using infrared rays, that is, with low germination, their germination rate increases with irradiation. We know that the natural moisture content of seeds for planting is enough to make it 10-15%. If the natural moisture content of the seeds that will be planted exceeds this value, the plant that will sprout from this seed will suffer from root rot and will die as a result. To prevent this from happening, seeds with high humidity are dried using infrared rays before planting. A plant that sprouts after irradiating seeds with infrared rays does not get sick, its root system is energetic, and the yield per hectare increases.

Applications check	The infrared rays	Ultra violetof uvraiolet rays
Medicinal seeds	Before planting, seeds,	Various bacteria kill the human body, grow and structure, and affect the skin tissue.
Agriculture used	1 food dry, it is before planting seeds, fertilizer, and organic phosphate analysis.	
The technique of drying	With different materials worked out, they look at the signal in bad cases, the amount of gasoline is determined by octane, and the composition of oil is studied by Surkov.	
The military sphere	Allows you to detect jet aircraft that launch missiles and satellites, while accurately pointing projectiles and missile carriers at the target, detecting camouflaged enemy objects.	
Astronomy	Brand determining the properties of the planet	
Photography	photos obtained by	Korongida allows you to keep invisible records, text that flew away when determining
the atmosphere	In the infrared radiation of the earth, the energy of the Universe goes into space, and the earth cools.	The atmosphere of a strong victory

CONCLUSION. Creative research of young people, teachers, activity, education, free meditation, directions, methods, and tools for the correct selection of interesting lectures, and debates should be rich, motivation for the emergence of creative disputes. Young people start these tasks no later than the initiative is in their hands, while the responsibility for directing certain key areas of their activity lies with the teacher, for monitoring general activities, for guiding in difficult situations, for advice from outside, such tasks as evaluating their activities remain. Technology education is a style of teaching innovation, so the goal is to provide students with the opportunity to promote knowledge of being, which is a form of knowledge and skills in relationships.

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